

**TEACHING COMPUTER STUDIES IN NIGERIA
SECONDARY SCHOOLS THROUGH THE USE OF
MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE-BASED ACTIVITIES AND
INDIVIDUALIZED LEARNING ACTIVITIES FOR
STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT**

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to examine the teaching of computer studies in Nigeria secondary schools through the use of multiple intelligence-based activities and individualized learning activities for students' achievement. Two research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The design was quasi-experimental. The population comprised of all 2022/2023 academic session of SS2 students offering computer studies in Awka Education zone of Anambra State. A sample of 181 SS2 students from 5 schools (87 males and 94 females) was drawn from the population using simple random sampling technique balloting without replacement. The experimental groups were taught with

multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA) and individualized learning activities (ILA) while the control group were taught with lecture method (LM) in each of the sample schools. Both the experimental and control groups were taught computer studies by their regular computer studies teachers. The instruments used for the study were Computer Studies Achievement Test (CSAT) which were validated by five experts. The reliability of the CSAT was determined using K-R₂₀ with index of 0.79. The research questions were answered using mean with standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA). The findings revealed that both MIBA and ILA significantly enhanced students' achievement in computer studies. However, the MIBA was more effective than ILA. This will ensure that computer studies teacher are adequately trained on how to use MIBA and ILA in teaching and learning.

Keywords: Multiple Intelligence-Based Activities, Individualized Learning Activities, Achievement.

Introduction

Computer studies is much more than ways of representing objects and processes, knowing how to use computer, applications and analyses that help to solve various human problems (O'Neill, Summers & Smith, 2021). This means that Computer studies is a subject that if effectively taught by competent teachers and with appropriate methods. Lecture method and instructional strategies used in Computer studies classroom seem to be inappropriate and uninspiring. The nature of Computer studies requires varied activities. Since learners acquire knowledge through various avenues, teachers need to select different strategies that could take care of learners' various learning needs, so as to actively engage in the process.

Multiple intelligence based activities (MIBA) as a teaching learning activities describe different ways learners learn, acquire information-knowledge and solve their problems through the acquired knowledge and skills. Samuel and Abba (2020) described MIBA as a framework that helps teachers design instruction based activities and provide varied learning experiences tailored for each learner. This implies that MIBA embraces instructional techniques that guide, direct, engage, motivate and foster learners' preference to learning. Rajadurai and Ganapathy (2023) added that MIBA are anchored in variety of intelligences by which individual learners function. The activities include observation, oral expression, analytical, creative and practical thinking activities as well as metacognitive processes.

The use of MIBA in teaching is based on intelligence quotient (IQ) (traditional notion of intelligence) learning theory propounded by Howard Gardner in 1983. Gardner's IQ learning theory states that learners are not born with all of the intelligences they will ever have. This theory challenged the traditional notion that there is one single type of intelligence sometimes known as "g" for general intelligence that only focuses on cognitive abilities. The theory further emphasized on how learners possess different kinds of minds for learning, remembering, performing and understanding in different ways. Thus, teachers are required to apply MIBA in classroom environment. Such activities employed in this study are collaborative learning, active learning, authentic instruction and self-assessment. This help to ascertain the intelligence they address. It implies that teachers require to provide learners with varied opportunities in the learning environment that could usher in learners' zeal and portray learners' potentials. They are also required to employ teaching method that gears towards generating individual learner's skills, learner's learning on their own pace and gaining self-confidence on their self.

Individualized learning activities (ILA) can also be called self-regulated (SRL), self-directed learning, self-paced learning or personalized learning. The theory was propounded by Fred Keller and Gilmour Sherman. The theory states that learners learn materials in small units. When they are ready, they take a test on the unit they have just completed and if they pass, they then move onto the next unit. Besides, in individualized learning, each learner progresses at his / her comfortable pace. This strategy does not require a coach or facilitator or a teacher during learning rather it frees the teachers from focusing on needs and problems of individual students.

Udu (2017) stressed that ILA could provide learners with the opportunity to grow in self-discipline, self-motivation, self-creativity and also present occasions for genuine interaction between the teacher and students which are future of multiple intelligence activities. Studies carried out by Udu (2017) and Loeng (2020) revealed that individual learners take decisions, initiative and responsibility for their own learning. These researchers employed instructional techniques such as adaptation, simulation, problem solving and self-assessment /evaluation. The present study would adopt only simulation and evaluation as one of the stated instructional techniques since there is need to introduce, adopt and adapt an instructional activity-oriented teaching-learning style that is individualistic in nature, takes cognizance of various learner's levels of intelligence which may be capable of improving learners creative ability, improve academic achievement of secondary school students in Computer studies.

Academic achievement can be attributed to great effort through hard work to succeed in one's activity. In relation to teaching and learning, it is the extent to which a learner is evaluated by the teacher or institution of learning to attain educational goals. Ogoke, Otumegwu and Nwaneri (2022) defined achievement or academic achievement as the act of accomplishing something successfully,

especially by means of exertion, skill, practice or perseverance. It is not only reaching greater heights but also getting something after a bit of struggle. Mbonu and Okoli (2019) defined academic achievement as the attained ability or degree of competence in school tasks, usually measured by standardized tests which is expressed in grades, based on norms derived from wide sampling of learners' academic ability.

Academic achievement equally connotes accomplishment of desired learning outcomes, thus achievement is determined by method of instruction, learning environment and the learner. That is to say that, achievement of learning objectives requires adoption and adaptation of multiple intelligence-based activities and individualized learning activities that could address learner's different intellectual abilities and as well provide individual learner opportunity to interact with the learning environment. Hence, this study on investigating the use of multiple intelligence-based activities and individualized learning activities in teaching computer studies in Nigeria secondary schools for students' achievement should be a worthwhile venture.

Statement of the Problem

Computer studies as a vocational subject at levels of education in Nigeria plays a vital role in learners' skill and entrepreneurship development, life-long learning and national development. The subject therefore requires to be taught by competent teachers who can use innovative methods of teaching and as well guide students towards achieving the desired educational goal. The available computer studies Chief examiners' reports of WASSCE May /June 2018-2022 reveals that there were improvement in some years and fluctuating in some other years. Hence, the problem of the present study is to find out if multiple intelligence-

based and individualized learning activities will improve and sustain male and female students' achievement in computer studies.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the use of multiple intelligence-based activities and individualized learning activities in teaching computer studies in Nigeria secondary schools for students' achievement. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Mean achievement scores of students taught Computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught with lecture method (LM).
2. Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer studies using MIBA, ILA and those taught using LM
3. Interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and LM) on students' achievement in Computer studies

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught Computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught using lecture method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught using lecture method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Computer studies with multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught with lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer studies using MIBA, ILA and those taught with lecture method.
3. There is no interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in Computer studies.

Methods

The study employed quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, the pretest post-test non-randomized control group design. According to Nworgu (2015), quasi-experimental designs establish cause and effect relationship between variables of interest in the study. Intact classes of computer studies students was used due to the fact that complete randomization of participants into groups was not possible. The study was carried out in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of the study consists of 905 (256 males and 649 females) SS 2 students for 2022 / 2023 academic session offering computer studies in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. The sample for the study consisted of 181 SS2 computer studies students drawn from the population. The sample was drawn through multistage sampling procedure. Specifically, multistage sampling procedure involves purposive sampling and simple random sampling techniques.

Firstly, purposive sampling technique was employed to select 20 public co-educational secondary schools in Awka education zone of Anambra State. This is because only 20 schools offer computer studies in external examination in Awka Education Zone. A simple random sampling technique (balloting without replacement) was used to select 5 public co-educational secondary schools. Intact classes from the 5 schools was used for both experimental and control groups. The choice of SS2 computer studies students was because they have been exposed to the subject for almost two years. The instrument for data collection are Computer Studies Achievement Test (CSAT). The instruments was validated by five experts and their comments were used to modify the instrument.

The reliability of CSAT was determined using one co-educational secondary school in Onitsha Education Zone of Anambra State which is outside the research area. One intact class of SS2 students with a total of 30 students offering computer studies was used. For CSAT reliability of the instrument was computed using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20. Its reliability index was 0.79

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught Computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught Computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and lecture method.

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Gained Mean	SD Pretest	SD Posttest
MIBA	70	28.26	62.51	34.25	11.42	20.19
ILA.	60	33.03	56.13	23.1	13.10	13.60
LECTURE	51	26.16	32.12	5.96	5.82	6.71

In Table 1, it was observed that the secondary students taught computer studies using multiple intelligence-base activities had pretest mean score of 28.26 with standard deviation of 11.42 in the pre-test achievement test and posttest mean score of 62.51, standard deviation of 20.19 with gained mean 34.25 in their achievement and the secondary students taught computer studies using individualized learning activities had pretest mean score of 33.03, standard deviation of 13.10 in the pre-test achievement test and posttest mean score of 56.13, standard deviation of 13.60 with gained mean 23.10 in their achievement. While those taught using lecture method had pretest mean score of 26.16 with standard deviation of 5.82 in the pre-test achievement test and posttest mean score of 32.12, standard deviation of 6.71 with gained mean 5.96. With posttest mean scores of 62.51 for MIBA and 56.13 for ILA which are above the decision rule of 50 multiple intelligence-base activities and individualized learning activities are effective in students' achievement scores in computer studies.

H0: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Computer studies with multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught with lecture method.

Table 2: MANCOVA on the achievement mean scores of secondary school students taught Computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities MIBA, ILA and lecture method

<u>Source of variation</u>	<u>SS</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>MS</u>	<u>Cal. F</u>	<u>Pvalue</u>	<u>Decision</u>
Corrected Model	36998.128	6	6166.355			
Intercept	32655.271	1	32655.271			
Achievement1	2263.580	1	2263.580			
Instructional Method	25693.250	2	12846.625	67.27	0.000	Sig
Gender	263.362	1	263.362	1.38	0.242	Not Sig
Instructional Method * Gender	4718.093	2	2359.047	12.35	0.000	Sig
Error	33230.900	174	190.982			
Total	556538.000	181				
Corrected Total	70229.028	180				

Table 2 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 2df numerator and 180df denominator, the calculated F is 67.27 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected. So, the difference in the posttest mean achievement scores of students taught Computer studies with multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities and those taught with lecture method is significant. To identify the direction of the differences in the mean achievement scores, a post hoc comparison of the three groups was done using Scheffe's test which is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Pair-Wise Comparison of the Achievement of MIBA, ILA and lecture method Using Scheffe's Test

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Posttest Achievement

Scheffe

(I)	(J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
MIBA	ILA	6.3810*	2.50558	.041	.1951	12.5669
	LM	30.3966*	2.62192	.000	23.9235	36.8698
ILA	MIBA	-6.3810*	2.50558	.041	-12.5669	-.1951

	LM	24.0157*	2.71245	.000	17.3191	30.7123
LM	MIBA	-30.3966*	2.62192	.000	-36.8698	-23.9235
	ILA	-24.0157*	2.71245	.000	-30.7123	-17.3191

Table 3 shows that there is a significant difference between MIBA and ILA at $P \leq 0.41$ with the mean achievement of 62.51 for MIBA being greater than ILA with the mean achievement of 56.13. However, Table 4 also reveals that there is a significant difference between MIBA and LM at $P \geq 0.5$ with the mean achievement scores of 62.51 for MIBA and 32.12 mean achievement for LM. Furthermore, Table 4 shows that there is a significant difference between ILA and MIBA at $P \leq 0.41$ with the mean achievement of 56.31 for ILA and 62.51 for MIBA. In addition, Table 4 reveals that there is a significant difference between ILA and LM at $P \geq 0.5$ with the mean achievement scores of 56.13 and LM mean of 32.12. Table 4 also reveals that there is a significant difference between LM and MIBA at $P \geq 0.5$ with the mean achievement scores of 62.51 for MIBA and LM mean of 32.12. Similarly, there is a significant difference between LM and ILA at $P \geq 0.5$ with the mean achievement scores of 32.12 for LM and 56.13 for ILA. Thus, the hypotheses that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught computer studies with MIBA, ILA and LM is rejected. Hence, the most effective method is MIBA followed by ILA.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught using lecture method?

Table 4: Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught computer studies using MIBA, ILA and lecture method.

Source of Variation	Gender	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Gained Mean	SD Pretest	SD Posttest
MIBA	Male	36	29.44	55.14	25.70	10.94	16.43
	Female	34	27.00	70.32	43.33	11.94	21.07
ILA	Male	31	28.06	52.00	23.94	13.34	15.01
	Female	29	27.55	55.86	28.31	10.75	9.22
LECTURE	Male	20	26.00	32.75	6.75	7.15	8.55
	Female	31	26.26	31.71	5.45	4.90	5.32

Table 4 reveals that male secondary students taught computer studies using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA) had pretest mean score of 29.44, SD pretest of 10.94 and posttest mean score of 55.14, SD posttest of 16.43 with gained mean 25.70 in their achievement while the female students taught using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA) had pretest mean score of 27.00, SD pretest of 11.94 and posttest mean score of 70.32, SD posttest of 21.07 with gained mean 43.33. With posttest gained mean scores of 25.70 for male students as against 43.33 for female students, MIBA is more effective in enhancing female secondary school students' achievement scores in computer studies.

Also male secondary students taught computer studies using individualized learning activities had pretest mean score of 28.06, SD pretest of 13.34 and posttest mean score of 52.00, SD posttest of 15.01 with gained mean 23.94 in their achievement while their female counterparts had pretest mean score of 27.55, SD pretest of 10.75 and posttest mean score of 55.86, SD posttest of 9.22 with gained mean 28.31. With gained mean scores of 23.94 for the male students and 27.55 for the female students, individualized learning activities is more effective in enhancing female secondary school students' achievement scores in computer studies.

Furthermore, male secondary students taught computer studies using lecture method had pretest mean score of 26.00, SD pretest of 7.15 and posttest mean score of 32.75, SD posttest of 8.55 with gained mean 6.75 in their achievement while their female counterparts had pretest mean score of 26.26, SD pretest of 4.90 and posttest mean score of 31.71, SD posttest of 5.32 with gained mean 5.45. With gained mean scores of 6.75 for the male students and 5.45 for the female students, lecture method is more effective in enhancing male secondary school students' achievement scores in computer studies.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer studies using MIBA, ILA and those taught with lecture method.

Table 5: MANCOVA on the mean scores of secondary school students taught Computer studies using MIBA, ILA and lecture method.

<u>Source of variation</u>	<u>SS</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>MS</u>	<u>Cal. F</u>	<u>Pvalue</u>	<u>Decision</u>
Corrected Model	36998.128	6	6166.355	32.288		
Intercept	32655.271	1	32655.271	170.986		
Achievement1	263.580	1	2263.580	11.852		
Instructional Method	25693.250	2	12846.625	67.266		
Gender	263.362	1	263.362	1.379	0.242*	Not Sig
Instructional Method * Gender	718.093	2	2359.047	12.352		
Error	33230.900	174	190.982			
Total	556538.000	181				
Corrected Total	70229.028	180				

Table 5 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 180df denominator, the calculated F is 1.38 with P value of 0.242 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is accepted. So, the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught using multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and those taught with lecture method is not significant.

H0₃: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in Computer studies.

Table 6: MANCOVA on the interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in Computer studies

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	Decision
Corrected Model	36998.128	6	6166.355	32.288		
Intercept	32655.271	1	32655.271	170.986		
Achievement1	263.580	1	2263.580	11.852		
Instructional Method	25693.250	2	12846.625	67.266		
Gender	263.362	1	263.362	1.379		
Instructional Method * Gender	718.093	2	2359.047	12.352	0.000	S
Error	33230.900	174	190.982			
Total	556538.000	181				
Corrected Total	70229.028	180				

Table 6 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 180df denominator, the calculated F is 12.35 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the fifth null hypothesis is not accepted. So, there is significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in Computer studies.

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Achievement1 = 29.2486

Figure 1: Plot of the interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in Computer studies.

The Plot of the interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in Computer studies is significant and ordinal. This shows that the teaching methods are gender sensitive. They are more effective in enhancing the female students achievement scores in computer studies.

Discussion

Results of data analysis in Table 1 has shown that the three methods (Multiple intelligence-base activities (MIBA), individualized learning activities (ILA) and Lecture method) were considered in this study. Meanwhile, further analysis of the results revealed that the MIBA and ILA were more effective in enhancing students' achievement than the lecture method. The finding agrees with the finding of Udu (2017) that method has significant effect on students' achievement. Also the findings of this study gave credence to the findings of Ekarika, Okon, Adie, Ajah and Odey (2022), Izuegbunam and Osuafor (2020), Fatokun and Samuel (2019), Gulcah and Halime (2018), Padmapriya (2015), Ali, Soosan and Hamze (2013) who in their separate studies found that Multiple intelligence-base activities (MIBA) and individualized learning activities (ILA) were more effective than the lecture method in enhancing students' achievement in science subjects.

Moreover, the relative effectiveness of MIBA and ILA over the lecture method in enhancing students' achievement could be attributed to the fact that both methods are activity-oriented and student centered which enable students to actively participate in teaching and lecturing unlike the lecture method. Given the prevailing circumstances under which the teaching methods were employed in

the classrooms, it is not surprising that the students taught with MIBA and ILA had higher achievement than those taught with the lecture method.

Furthermore, this study found that the MIBA was more effective than the ILA in enhancing students' academic achievement. The effectiveness of MIBA over ILA could stem from the fact that students have the tendency to learn from their peers through peer interactivity and discovery of new knowledge through different activities in the classroom, unlike individualized learning activities where the student carry out activities on individual bases.

Evidence of the result in Table 4 revealed that the mean gain of MIBA is 17.63 whereas the SD for the pretest for male is 10.94, 11.94 for female. SD posttest for male is 16.43 and 21.07 for female. In the same vein, the mean gain of ILA is 0.73 whereas the SD for the pretest for male is 13.34, 10.75 for female. SD posttest for male is 15.01 and 9.22 for female. Mean gain of lecture method is 1.3 whereas the SD for the pretest for male is 7.15, 4.90 for female. SD posttest for male is 8.55 and 5.32 for female. In other to find out if the difference in the mean achievement scores between the male and female students in the three groups was significant or not, multivariate analysis of covariance were used. The result of the study portrayed that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught computer studies using MIBA, ILA and lecture method. This shows that gender has no significant influence on students' achievement. This agrees with Okekeokosisi and Okigbo (2019), Alao (2017) and Okekeokosisi and Okigbo (2013) who in their separate studies found no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students in computer studies. However, the finding of this study disagreed with Dawal (2021), Samuel and Abba (2020) and Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) who found significant difference in the achievement of male and female students in Basic Science and technology, Genetics and Social studies respectively. Moreso,

the female students' mean achievement in the multiple intelligence-base activities (MIBA) and individualized learning activities (ILA) was found to be slightly higher than that of the male students while the male students mean achievement in lecture method was higher than that of the female students. This can be attributed to the fact that the students were exposed to different teaching environments; MIBA, ILA and lecture method. It then shows that the female students achieved higher in MIBA environment and ILA environment while the male students achieved higher in a lecture method environment. The observed differences however were not significant. This means that gender has no significant influence on the academic achievement of students in computer studies when student-centered and activity based teaching strategies are employed by the teachers.

The study on interaction effect of gender and teaching method on students' achievement in computer studies was significant and disordinal. This shows that the teaching methods are gender sensitive. Besides, the result of this study contradicts with the findings of Udu (2017) and Ezeh (2013) who found that the interaction effect of method and gender on students' achievement was not significant. Thus, the need for the present study.

Conclusion

The findings from the study showed that multiple intelligence-based activities (MIBA) and individualized learning activities (ILA) are effective in enhancing secondary school students' achievement in computer studies. The study also points that there is significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods (MIBA, ILA and lecture method) on students' achievement scores in computer studies. This implies that the methods are gender sensitive. Based on the findings, it is concluded that there is significant interaction effect between teaching methods and gender on students' achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teacher education programmes should include MIBA and ILA in computer studies teaching method. This will ensure that computer studies teachers are adequately trained on how to use MIBA and ILA in teaching and learning.
2. Curriculum planners should emphasize more on the use of MIBA and ILA in teaching and learning of computer studies so as to popularize its use among teachers.

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